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Enhancing Students' Sociocultural Awareness through a Discursive Approach to Literary Texts

378.091

Abstract: *The article presents some methodological aspects of the development of sociocultural competence in English classes through a discursive approach to the literary text. Sociocultural competence is a set of knowledge, skills,*

and attitudes that generate the good cultural behaviors required for an efficient integration in cultural situations. The didactic potentiality of a literary text depends on the approach used in the classroom. In this regard, the article points out the role of the discursive approach to the literary text in the development of students' sociocultural sensibility.

Keywords: *sociocultural competence, skills, literary text, discursive approach, development.*

Rezumat: *Articolul prezintă unele aspecte metodologice ale dezvoltării competenței socioculturale la lecțiile de limbă engleză prin abordarea discursivă a textului literar. Competența socioculturală este un ansamblu de cunoștințe, abilități și atitudini care generează bunele comportamente culturale necesare pentru o integrare eficientă în situații culturale. Posibilitățile didactice ale unui text literar depind de abordarea folosită în clasă. În acest sens, articolul subliniază rolul și necesitatea abordării discursive a textului literar în dezvoltarea sensibilității socioculturale a studenților în cadrul orelor de limbă engleză.*

Cuvinte-cheie: *competență socioculturală, abilitate, text literar, abordare discursivă, dezvoltare.*

The development of sociocultural competence involves a perception of cultural self-reflection along with an apprehension of the cultural reflection of the target culture and one's ability to estimate this reflection with reality. But it is not reflection alone that characterizes sociocultural competence. It is also developed and demonstrated by the speaker's attitude and interpretation.

Sociocultural competence is always evolving according to social needs or life circumstances. Hence, sociocultural competence is defined as a set of knowledge, skills, and attitudes that generate the good cultural behaviors required for an efficient integration in cultural situations. Sociocultural competence comprises a number of abilities and attitudes, such as: expressing one's point of view and cultural values; openness and interest towards foreign people, societies, and cultures; establishing human relationships based on cultural values; mediating between one's own culture and the acquired foreign culture with a view to appease conflicts.

Sociocultural competence is acquired when integrating the individuals' knowledge into specific practices and cultural environments [4]. From this perspective, literary texts contain a number of elements of a nation's culture and are a useful source of learning. They are a cultural product to which the learners have access. The literary text helps the students learn about the social, political, and historical events that constitute the setting of the text.

When studying or analyzing a literary text the students get acquainted with different life situations and propose

interpretative solutions. They may have different points of view, which lead to an opinion gap, but the literary text gives them examples of problem-solving through interaction, dialogue, and communication. The literary text is an expression of society. It does not portray humans in search of themselves. The literary text has become a contiguity of the cultural quintessence of a family, of a nation, of a community as it touches the highest level of life.

The potentiality of a literary text depends on the didactic approach employed by the teacher. A discursive approach considers the literary text as a resource that stimulates the acquisition of language structures. The literary text may illustrate a number of styles and registers, which generate various interpretations and discussions focused on social, cultural, and life topics. The interpretation of literary texts through a discursive approach involves studying the linguistic features of the text in order to understand how the meanings are conveyed. Therefore, a discursive approach to the literary text represents a way of interpreting it in which the narrator and the reader build judgements/messages/arguments that belong to broader social practices. It also studies the types of relationships between these two actors; the linguistic units used to render the truths; the way of appreciating statements and their meaning in different communication practices [3].

A well-chosen literary text, along with appropriate teaching activities, creates multiple interpretative benefits for the students. Taking into consideration the characteristics of the discourse, we will explore a set of strategies

for a discursive approach to the literary text that favor the development of sociocultural communication skills in the English language. Some of these strategies are: discursive strategies of description, explanation, persuasion, argumentation, dramatization, and modifiers. Thus, interpreting these strategies used in the literary text, the learners will become skillful enough to use them in their daily activities and real life situations. The skills formed in the classroom will help them cope with much more complex situations.

We will illustrate with a range of activities that encourage the development of communicative competence (namely the sociocultural component) at the following stages: *Pre-task*, *Task-cycle* and *Post-task* on the basis of an excerpt from the novel *Pride and Prejudice* by Jane Austen.

At the *Pre-Task* stage the learners get acquainted with the facts that will lead them to the understanding of the content when interpreting it. It is a preparatory level before contact with the text. The teacher proposes a series of introductory activities needed for the building of a workable atmosphere, which will help the learners to perceive the text accurately and deeply. The diversity of the tasks, activities, and strategies used in the language classroom is of great value, since all dimensions of communicative competence are improved through reception, mediation, and production activities. At this stage the teacher uses activities and tasks of various nature in order to guide the students towards discovery and enhance their interest towards the text. Thus, the teacher creates different learning settings, aiming to help the students acquire new relevant knowledge. Should the students encounter difficulties, the teacher helps with explanations and elucidations. Mediation activities may be employed in order to facilitate the understanding of certain ideas and concepts from the relevant sociocultural knowledge system.

In this light, the *Pre-task* stage favors the study of the discursive specificity of the text – more specifically, the context and the conditions in which the text had been written. To this end the teacher may use reception activities with tasks intended for text comprehension, such as:

Develop a mind map pointing out all the words that belong to the following concepts: a) music; b) neighborhood; c) party.

Formulate the quintessence of the concept of culture and underline the importance of culture in the formation of people's demeanor and attitudes.

Identify the sociocultural norms and values of the 19th century. Find some efficient ways to address them.

Mention 5 examples of good-mannered behavior a young man may demonstrate at a party in our days and 5 examples for a similar setting in the 19th century.

At this stage the learning settings promote integration for the *Task-Cycle* stage. At the **Task-Cycle stage**, learners get familiar with the content of the text. This is the stage where the text is perceived and mediated. The teacher proposes various activities in order to ensure an efficient

interpretation of the text. Such activities contain tasks based on solving contextual problems, exploring and finding meaningful solutions, denoting interactive and constructive learning. The task goes through three phases: the task is developed and presented to the learners; they plan and sketch a way of solving/fulfilling the task.

A discursive analysis of the literary text at this stage implies a study of the language structures of the text: vocabulary, terminology, the use of certain grammatical patterns (amplifiers, nouns, euphemisms, politeness markers, causative, modal, spatial, and temporal markers, stylistic devices, and rhetorical effects), a description of prototypical textual sequences (description, narration, explanation, argumentation etc.), as well as multimodal and evaluative markers. Therefore, the learners have an opportunity to exercise a series of skills developed in the process of thinking, analyzing, acting, and communicating about a wide range of situations from the story. They develop sociocultural and pragmatic skills when receiving and producing oral and written messages. The tasks range from the simple to the complex, serving as a transition from analytical thinking to discursive actions, i.e. the tasks valorize the impact of the communicative situation.

The integrative tasks exploit a situation-problem, a question or issue the learners may face outside the classroom. The teacher uses productive and cultural activities for the tasks suggested by the text. Examples:

Using the Star Explosion technique, ask questions related to the text content, focusing on the main characters of the novel: Mr. and Mrs. Bennet, Mr. Bingley, Mr. Darcy, and Elizabeth Bennet (*Who? What? When? Where? How?*). The questions will cover certain semantic structures and connotations reflected in the text. It is an efficient production activity, as it contributes to the formulation of questions connected to the ideas of the text, but also relevant to real-life situations.

Paraphrase the statement and identify a 19th-century mother's wish. Does it correspond to 21st-century realities? Identify the similarities and the differences. Point out the socio-cultural hints revealed by the statement.

Explain the author's choice of literary style and rewrite the belletristic speech in a colloquial style. Through discursive tasks such as reformulation, transformation, paraphrasing, and rewriting the teacher helps the students comprehend the message, establish the sociocultural specifics, and accept the system of sociocultural values in general.

Think about the suggested situation and reenact it: Darcy realizes that Elizabeth is gossiping with her sister about him in an unpleasant way. He is disturbed to hear their opinion of himself and decides to change their mind so they may see him in a positive light. What remarks would he use to begin the conversation and convince the girls of the opposite? Use politeness formulae. This type of suggested settings will generate more communicative situations, which will help the learner integrate into a real-life context.

Find arguments that the excerpt has a comic tone, or, in Jane Austen's own words, 'light and bright, and sparkling'. Develop clusters and fill them with the linguistic units that emphasize a sarcastic, ironic, and comical tone. Elucidate their meanings. While reading the students point out the words or turns of phrase that weave the sarcastic/ironic or comical web of the text, express ideas, and discover connotations. All their ideas are valorized with the help of the *Clustering* technique, an efficient tool for structuring and organizing thoughts. The semantic or connotative hints contained in the text take the learners to the study of the social context. By exploring the linguistic instruments employed by the author the learners gain knowledge and improve their sociocultural awareness of British 19th-century society as reflected in the novel.

At this stage the teacher may propose activities that aim to develop the students' skills for *comparing, analyzing, associating,* and *arguing* facts. The *Cube* technique is perfectly suitable for this purpose. Example:

The novel is set in Longbourn during the Napoleonic Wars (1797-1815). Working with the text, point out the characteristic traits of those times (culture, value, manners, attitudes, lifestyles, prejudices, speech etc.). Support your ideas with relevant language structures and examples. The *Cube* covers such thinking operations as: *describe, associate, compare, analyze, use, argue,* and *illustrate*. The cube passes through the classroom and the learners bring forth their arguments according to the requirements from the face of the cube. Consequently, all the aspects of the text will be properly explored so that there may be a complex integration of the text content.

At the **Post-Task** stage we may use activities meant for identifying and evaluating various aspects of the text content. At this stage the teacher employs discursive tasks, which make the learner *reason, argue, support his opinion, compare, identify, justify, speculate, illustrate, connect,* and *form personal judgments*, which produce interaction and discussions of various kinds. Such tasks will help the learners to acquire the social skills that will enable them to get along with others and act with confidence.

At this stage, where the acquired knowledge, skills, and attitudes are being assessed, the teacher may use such strategies as will help the learners organize, review, and check their understanding: *case study, role simulation, mind maps, mini-projects*. Examples:

You are Mr. Bingley. Explain to Elizabeth why your friend refuses to interact with her. Role-play with your classmate. Pay attention to the choice of conversation starters, greetings, forms of address, excuses, and rejection of apologies.

Taking into account the characters' manners and speech patterns, classify in a T-Graph those acceptable and objectionable in 19th-century, as well as in modern society.

Create a web quest. Open the link <https://www.canva.com/> and make a presentation about Great Britain in the 19th century. The learners work in groups; each group searches for information about one of the following aspects: *fashion, literature, arts, school,* and *entertainment*. Having gathered the information, they will then create collages, adding brief notes, pieces of music and videos in order to make their presentations as original and interesting as possible. The project aims to develop products that help the teacher review what the students have learned.

Write an essay about your country's specific national features – such as clothing, occupations, and traditions – in the 19th century, using 10 discursive markers (600 words).

The literary texts whose authors belong to other cultures contain a wide spectrum of values, social thinking, consciousness, attitudes, and understanding of different perspectives, as well as empathy for others, associated with the event or subject under study. The students' perception of text sequences and scenes gives them the possibility to gain awareness concerning sociocultural differences and be more tolerant, open, sympathetic, and flexible. A complex study of text language contributes to the development of students' communicative competence, as it teaches them how to use language in society. The discursive practices used for text analysis generate social skills and sociocultural awareness. In conclusion, literary texts can be useful for the learners who have no or little social experience by prompting them to make connections with real life and by stimulating research into challenging social and cultural issues.

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